

**MODERN CHALLENGES AND SOLUTIONS IN ONLINE COURSE QUALITY
MANAGEMENT**

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Abstract: The article provides a comparative analysis of online education quality management systems in Russia and abroad. The authors note the rapid development of distance learning formats, which has been accelerated by the pandemic, and identify a key problem: the lack of unified formalized mechanisms for assessing the quality of online education. Based on a study of domestic and international practices, significant differences in approaches have been identified. In Russia, regulation is primarily based on the general provisions of the Law on Education and methodological recommendations, while quality assessment is fragmented and departmental. In foreign practice (USA, EU), specialized international standards (ISO 21001), industry-specific accreditation systems (e.g., Quality Matters), and uniform rubrics for course evaluation are widely used. As a scientific contribution, the authors propose a model for assessing the quality of online courses based on four criteria: content effectiveness, technological reliability, organizational support, and performance. A comparative analysis presented in tabular form clearly demonstrates the lag of the Russian system in terms of standardization, external accreditation, the use of unified metrics, and adaptive learning technologies. The authors conclude that the Russian system of online education quality management is still in the process of development and requires standardization. It is recommended to adapt the proposed model based on international experience and modern digital analysis methods to increase the level of trust and effectiveness of online learning in Russia.

Keywords: quality management, online education, distance learning, standardization, comparative analysis, accreditation, assessment model.

Relevance. Currently, online education is rapidly developing. In 2019, its volume was estimated at USD 205 billion [1]. The pandemic has increased interest in remote formats, but the lack of formalized quality assessment mechanisms remains a challenge [2]. A comparative analysis of different approaches to education quality will not only improve the level of online education on domestic platforms, but also contribute to increasing the effectiveness of education and enhancing the trust of students and teachers in online education. Therefore, the study of the quality of online education is relevant both in the scientific community and among various organizations that provide educational services. This article examines the features of quality management in Russia and abroad.

The goal is to conduct a comparative analysis of approaches to managing the quality of online education in Russia and abroad.

The objectives are to study the specifics of Russian and foreign regulation and propose a model for assessing the quality of online courses.

Russian experience.

When conducting the study, it was revealed that in the Russian Federation, the introduction of online education is actively taking place both in the system of additional and higher education. The Ministry of Science and Higher Education and other agencies are developing methodological recommendations, but formal regulatory criteria of quality often come down to the general provisions of the Federal Law “On Education”.[1] Individual universities and educational portals (for example, “Fokus”, “Uchi.ru”, “Yandex.Uchebnik”, etc.) are developing their own methods of monitoring the quality of materials and academic performance, but the approaches vary greatly. Leading domestic platforms (Uchi.ru, RESH, YClass, Internet Lesson, etc.) offer

different models: some are more focused on supporting schools and students (government projects), while others offer mass courses from private companies.

Foreign experience.

During the study, it was found that abroad, the issues of the quality of online education are regulated more formally through international standards and accreditation. For example, the international organization ISO has developed the ISO 21001 standard, “Management Systems of Educational Organizations”, which aims to improve the quality of educational services and meet the needs of students.[3] Similar standards (e.g. ISO 29993) cover various forms of continuing education. At the level of universities and courses, the practice of external certification is widely used.[4] One example is the American organization Quality Matters (QM), which has formalized rubrics for assessing the quality of online course design since 2005. QM has developed criteria and tools for evaluating the content, pedagogical methods, and technical support of a course. [2] According to a study by the Higher School of Economics, the QM system is one of the most popular tools for assessing the quality of online courses.

The proposed evaluation model.

Based on the analysis, four criteria were identified: 1) content effectiveness (this criterion includes the content, logic, and relevance of the educational content), 2) technological reliability (this criterion characterizes the quality of the digital environment through which online learning takes place, the usability of the interface, and accessibility for users), 3) organizational support (the structure of the course and the qualifications of the instructor), and 4) effectiveness (this criterion measures the satisfaction of students after completing the educational program and the acquisition of practical knowledge) [5]. Each criterion can be evaluated through a set of indicators, such as the percentage of successful graduates. The study conducted a comparative analysis of quality management in online education in Russia and abroad. The results of the analysis are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Comparative Characteristics of Online Education Quality Management Systems

Criteria	Russia	Foreign countries
Regulatory framework	General educational standards (FGOS), methodological recommendations from the Ministry of Education; there are few special laws/standards for online formats.	International standards ISO 21001, ESG (EU), national laws; industry-specific (e.g., QM for the USA) and UNESCO industry-specific recommendations.
Accreditation and QA	State accreditation of programs also covers distance learning; there are no specialized regulatory bodies for online learning..	Clear procedures for external accreditation of online courses, course authentication (e.g., QM certification), and external auditors and regulators.
Course evaluation metrics	Mostly internal: exam/survey scores, faculty reports. Few unified metrics.	Use of unified rubrics (Quality Matters, OLC Rubric, ISO 21001 guidelines), and analysis of big data on learning (Learning Analytics)..
Technological support	Use of domestic and foreign LMS (Moodle, Canvas, etc.). Infrastructure development is often fragmented.	Wide adoption of advanced technologies (MOOC platforms, artificial intelligence for personalization, and adaptive learning).
Feedback and	Feedback is collected through	Strict regular (anonymous)

Criteria	Russia	Foreign countries
adaptation	surveys/forums; it is less integrated. Course improvements are often initiated by the author	questionnaires, A/B testing of forms and content, and regular course revisions by external experts.

Conclusions. The analysis shows that the domestic online education management system is still in the process of development. An analysis of online education in other countries (USA, UK, EU) reveals that most developed countries focus on developing standards, implementing advanced technologies in online education, and receiving feedback from consumers. The Russian model requires standardization and unification. The proposed model can serve as a basis for evaluating the quality of courses and can be adapted to the Russian context. It is recommended to rely on international experience and digital analysis methods [3; 4; 5].

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